

Deliverable 8.1

Driver validation report of Year 2 EOSC-ENTRUST architectural blueprint including gap analysis

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Authors	Anne van der Kant (Health-RI), Deborah Wiltshire (GESIS), Beate Lichtwardt (UKDS), Péter HEGEDŰS (TARKI), Romina Royo Garrido (BSC), Marcos Casado Barbero (EMBL-EBI), Amy Curwin (CRG), Maria Panagiotopoulou (ECRIN), Christian Ohmann (ECRIN), Christian Cole (UNIVDUN), Chris Hall (UNIVDUN), Russel Gene Wolff (UiO), Milen Kouylekov (UiO), Rob Baxter (HDR UK), Jussi Salmi (TUAS), Susanna Repo (CSC), Srishti Dang (Health-RI)		
Contributors			
Acknowledgements (not grant participants)			
Reviewers	Ulriika Vihervalli (CSC), Miikka Kallberg (CSC), Jan-Willem Boiten (Health-RI)		

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1. Executive Summary

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability between TREs by development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis. The project is supported by four driver projects (hereafter Drivers), i.e. use cases which are prototypic for federated, multinational use of TREs in research practice across scientific domains and user communities:

- **Federated Human Genomics** as a catalyst for European TRE provision (EMBL, CRG, BSC, CSC)
- Common standards to enable trans-national sharing of **administrative and social science data** (CESSDA, GESIS, UKDS, TARKI)
- Enabling the re-use of **clinical trials data** for research purposes across Europe (ECRIN, UiO, HDR UK, UNIVDUN)
- **Public-Private interactions** between TRE in health and environmental data (Turku UAS, CSC, Sigma2)

The Drivers (united in WP7/8/9) both inform and validate the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint¹ and provide user input to TRE providers by stating their requirements for TREs.

This deliverable presents four prototypes developed by the four Drivers with the aim of validating the second year version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework (ENTRUST Blueprint/ Blueprint). To validate the second EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint, the four Drivers performed a gap analysis between the Blueprint and the prototypes as well as the more general Driver requirements. This deliverable presents the results of this gap analysis and discusses general versus Driver-specific gaps and recommendations that follow from those for the final installment of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint.

This deliverable contributes to the overall project objectives by validating the second year version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework (Blueprint) against real-world use cases. These will be used by WP14 (Architecture) to update and extend the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint and by WP17 (AAAI) to validate and refine the AAAI architecture. Furthermore, TRE Providers, united in WP11, will use the updated requirements to assess community needs. The updated requirements also form a basis for the further development of the requirements management framework developed by WP11. Lastly, the prototypes of Driver 1 and Driver 3 provide a real-world validator of the federated workflow processing technology developed in WP20.

¹ Sætrom, P., Lehvälaiho, H., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., & Hesam, A. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4 Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14362388>

2. Contribution towards project objectives

The D8.1 deliverable report contributes to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No. and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	No
	2. A ‘starter pack’ of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	Yes
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	No
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	No
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18)	No
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a European framework using common standards and shared legal,	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	No
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	No
	3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. Define the security baseline and auditing	No

operational and technical language.	procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes ² principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15)	
	5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC-compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
<p>Objective 3</p> <p>National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes</p>	1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	No
	2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).	No
	3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.</p>	1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).	No
	2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).	No
	3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).	No
	4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)	Yes

² Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

3. Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full form
AAAI	Authentication, Authorisation, Auditing and Accounting Infrastructure
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BAM	Binary Alignment Map, file format for raw genome sequencing data
BSC	Barcelona Supercomputing Center
BY-COVID	Beating pandemics by integrating data, tools and cohorts
CDISC	Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CLARIAH	Common Lab Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
CRC	Colorectal Cancer
crDSR	clinical research Data Sharing Repository
CRG	Centre for Genomic Regulation
CSC	CSC - IT Center for Science Ltd., TRE provider located in Finland
D	Deliverable
DAA	Data Access Agreement
DAC	Data Access Committee
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPA	Data Processing Agreement
ECRIN	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network
EGA	European Genome-phenome Archive
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EMBL-EBI	EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute
ENTRUST	European Network of Trusted Research Environments

EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EuroHPC	European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FEGA	Federated European Genome-Phenome Archive
FL	Federated Learning
Five Safes	Framework for safe data access (Safe People, Projects, Data, Settings, Outputs)
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GESIS	GESIS Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences, TRE provider located in Germany
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HDAB	Health Data Access Body
HDR UK	Health Data Research UK, UK national institute for health data science
HIC	Health Informatics Centre, TRE provider at University of Dundee, UK
HPC	High Performance Computing
ICD-10	International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision
IP	Intellectual Property
IPD	Individual Participant Data
Joint Controller	Joint Data Controller under GDPR
KB	National Library of the Netherlands (Koninklijke Bibliotheek)
LSOA	Lower Layer Super Output Area
MedDRA	Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities
MPC	Multi-Party Computation
MS	Milestone
NHS	National Health Service
NISV	Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision

ODISSEI	Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
ONS	Office for National Statistics, UK
PCAWG	Pan-Cancer Analysis of Whole Genomes
PI	Principal Investigator
QMZ	Quarantine / Quality Management Zone
RAZ	Restricted Access Zone
RCT	Randomized Controlled Trial
RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
RUC	Rural–Urban Classification
RWD	Real World Data
SANE	Secure ANalysis Environment
SATRE	Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments
SD Connect	Secure data transfer service (CSC)
SD Desktop	Secure Desktop (CSC)
SD Services	Services for Sensitive Data (CSC)
SDC	Statistical Disclosure Control
Sigma2	Service provider for national e-infrastructure in Norway
SLURM	Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management
SOPs	Standard Operating Procedures
SPE	Secure Processing Environment
SSO	Single Sign On
SURF	Dutch collaborative ICT organisation for education and research
TARKI	TÁRKI Social Research Institute, applied social research centre located in Hungary
TES	Task Execution Service

TRE	Trusted Research Environment
TSD	Services for Sensitive Data, TRE provider at UiO, Norway
Turku UAS	Turku University of Applied Sciences
UiO	University of Oslo
UKDS	UK Data Service, TRE provider located in the UK
UNIVDUN	University of Dundee, UK
WfExS	Workflow Execution Service
WP	Work Package

4. Introduction

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to further enhance interoperability between Trusted Research Environments (TREs) and federated sensitive data access and analysis in Europe by creating a European network of TREs and developing a common blueprint for TRE federation. The project is supported by four driver projects (hereafter Drivers) which provide real-world use cases which are exemplary for federated, multinational use of TREs in research practice across scientific domains and user communities:

- **Federated Human Genomics** as a catalyst for European TRE provision (partners: EMBL, CRG, BSC, CSC; TREs: SD Services (CSC), BSC TRE)
- Common standards to enable trans-national sharing of **administrative and social science data** (partners: CESSDA, GESIS, UKDS, TARKI; TREs: GESIS TRE, UKDS, Tarki (under development))
- Enabling the re-use of **clinical trials data** for research purposes across Europe (partners: ECRIN, UiO, HDR UK, UNIVDUN; TREs: TSD (UiO), HIC (UNIVDUN))
- **Public-Private interactions** between TREs in health and environmental data (partners: Turku UAS, CSC, Sigma2; TRE: SD Services (CSC))

The Drivers (united in WP7/8/9) both inform and validate the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint by (1) stating their requirements for TREs, (2) informing TRE providers about user needs and (3) using real-world exemplars to validate Blueprint versions and recommend adaptations.

In November 2024, the Architecture WP (WP13) delivered the first year version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework (from now on: Blueprint)³. This Blueprint version contained the first architectural design, focusing on (technical) components that both individual TREs and a federation of TREs need to operate. During the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint Validation Workshop, held as a hybrid meeting in Utrecht, January 21-22, 2025, the first year Blueprint was validated against the initial Driver requirements reported in MS7 (MS7 Initial Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers⁴) through a gap analysis. This led to multiple recommendations which were described in the first Drivers deliverable (D7.1: Driver validation report of Year 1 EOSC-ENTRUST architectural blueprint including gap analysis⁵). In addition, the Drivers published a revised set of requirements in August 2025 (MS8: Revised Driver Requirements

³ Sætrom, P., Lehvslaiho, H., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., & Hesam, A. (2024). EOSC-ENTRUST D13.4 Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14362388>

⁴ van der Kant, A., & Boiten, J.-W. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST MS7 Initial Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17434188>

⁵ van der Kant, A., Boiten, J.-W., Rujano, M. A., Ohmann, C., Gonzalo Jimenez, E., Tuikka, A.-M., Wiltshire, D., Casado Barbero, M., Lichtwardt, B., & Bolton, S. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST D7.1 Driver validation report of Year 1 EOSC-ENTRUST architectural blueprint including gap analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14988869>

for TREs from the four Drivers⁶), including a mapping of Driver requirements to capitalize architecture elements.

The second year version of the ENTRUST Blueprint (D14.3 Year two version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework⁷), published November 2025, includes a glossary of terminologies and the first versions of template legal agreements, operating procedures, and interface definitions in addition to updated architecture specifications. Both the recommendations from D7.1 and the mapping from MS8 were integrated in the second year version of the Blueprint by WP 13 (Architecture). The D14.3 deliverable describes in detail how recommendations and requirements from the Drivers were integrated in the architecture. In short, key additions include:

- An *Agreement* type was introduced to the *Registry service* of the *Federation Services* to support the Drivers' requirements for the federation to support a variety of agreements.
- The element *Data access requests* was added to the *Discovery Service*, as well as the user role of *Access Requester*. To support the processing of data access requests, this capability was also added to the *Secure Data Archive* and *Secure Data Holder* components within TREs, as well as the role of *Data Access Approver*.
- Tools for *Data terminology / standards conversion* and *data quality checks* were added to the *Software Service* with the remark that these are examples of possible tools supported by the *Software Service*, but that the scope is much broader.
- *User support* was added to the *Federation Services* to allow for ongoing user support within the federation.

This report uses Driver prototypes, i.e. real world implementations of (parts of) the first ENTRUST Blueprint, in combination with Driver requirements and their experienced barriers to implementation, to validate the second Blueprint and provide recommendations for the final version of the ENTRUST Blueprint. In the gap analysis, the Drivers have widened their focus along with the second year Blueprint: from architecture specifications only to including Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), legal framework, roles and terminology. Since Drivers could not yet implement the proposed interface definitions since the time of publication of the second Blueprint (November, 2025), these could not be validated in the current iteration. By using real-world prototypes, Drivers have also been able to identify some barriers to adoption. In Chapter 5, Methods, the approach that was taken in the gap analysis is described in more detail. The Drivers' prototypes, as well as each Driver's gap analysis results, are described in Chapter 6, Description of work accomplished.

⁶ van der Kant, A., Dang, S., Panagiotopoulou, M., Casado Barbero, M., Curwin, A. J., Tuikka, A.-M., Wiltshire, D., Bolton, S., & Lichtwardt, B. (2025). EOSC-ENTRUST MS8 Revised Driver Requirements for TREs from the four Drivers report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17376746>

⁷ Sætrom, P., Lehväslaiho, H., Stansberg, C., Awan, H., Dijkstra, F., Winge, I., & Hesam, A. (2026). EOSC-ENTRUST D14.3 Year two version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299343>

5. Methods

5.1 Prototype development

Each Driver developed a prototype testing (elements of) the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint during the year 2025. These prototypes are intended to provide real-world implementations of parts of the first version of the Blueprint (the second version was published after building the prototypes was largely completed). The prototypes vary in their focus and in which elements of the Blueprint they test, according to the Driver's specific needs and challenges. Due to the variety in setup, the development of the prototypes is detailed in each Driver's section. The following prototypes were developed by the Drivers:

- **Driver 1** worked together with WP19/20/21 to **run a data analysis workflow over two TREs and combine the results in one of the TREs** in an automated way.
- **Driver 2** used a **third-party secure environment** (SANE) to support **cross-border data access without travel**, while the data remain under the control of GESIS.
- **Driver 3** analysed **clinical trial data and real-world data in two separate TREs and combines the results**.
- **Driver 4** generated **synthetic data based on sensitive source datasets in a TRE**, thus taking a different approach to keeping data secure by making a synthesised version of sensitive data sharable outside TREs.

5.2 Blueprint gap analysis

5.2.1 Gap analysis in 2nd EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint validation workshop

A gap analysis of the second ENTRUST Blueprint was performed by the Drivers with support from other WPs during the *2nd EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint validation workshop*, held online.

Date:

Held online on 2–3 December 2025

- Day 1 (2 December 2025): 13:00–17:00 CET
- Day 2 (3 December 2025): 09:00–13:00 CET

Aim of the session:

The workshop focused on refining and validating the second version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint through in-depth engagement with the Driver prototypes. The objectives were to review key updates to the Blueprint, discuss ongoing challenges, and align across Drivers and Work Packages on essential topics such as architecture specifications, legal frameworks, standard operating procedures (SOPs), roles, and common terminology.

Through showcases of the Driver prototypes, breakout sessions, and cross-driver discussions, participants collaboratively identified remaining gaps and defined next steps towards full federation readiness.

Participants:

The workshop was attended by a broad range of consortium members, including representatives from each Driver under WP8 (Drivers 1–4), as well as participants from other relevant Work Packages (WP2, WP11, WP14, WP17, and WP20), ensuring balanced representation across Drivers, technical experts, and domain stakeholders.

Structure:

Day 1 started with a welcome and introduction, during which the workshop objectives, scope, and expected outcomes were outlined. This was followed by a deep dive into the second-year EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint, highlighting key updates, changes since the previous version, and the areas requiring validation and feedback from the Drivers.

Subsequently, short showcases of the Driver prototypes were presented by each Driver (Drivers 1–4). These presentations focused on:

- The aim and scope of each Driver
- The capabilities currently demonstrated by the prototype in relation to the Blueprint
- Identified limitations, open challenges, and aspects not yet addressed

Building on the prototypes, the afternoon of Day 1 was dedicated to Driver-specific breakout sessions on **Topic #1: Architecture specifications and Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs)**. Using a common breakout template and supported by preparation materials, participants assessed the alignment between Blueprint requirements and prototype implementations. Gaps were recorded in the common breakout template. The day concluded with a plenary cross-Driver alignment session, during which key matches, mismatches, and initial gaps identified in the breakouts were discussed and commonalities and differences between Drivers were identified.

Day 2 began with a brief reflection on Day 1 outcomes and a recap of objectives for the second day. The main Day 2 focus was on continued Blueprint validation through thematic breakout sessions per Driver, addressing:

- **Topic #2: Legal framework**, including legal roles, responsibilities, and compliance considerations
- **Topic #3: Roles and common terminology**, supported by the project glossary to ensure consistency across Drivers

Following the breakouts, a plenary cross-Driver alignment session was held to compare outcomes, identify common patterns, and further refine and harmonise gaps across Drivers. This led to the identification of both Driver-specific and common gaps.

Output method:

- Minutes and action points were captured using standardized templates.
- Identified gaps were reviewed, harmonized across Drivers, and consolidated.
- These harmonized gaps form a key input and foundation for the development of the final version of the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint.

5.2.3 Topics & questions gap analysis

Architecture specifications

For the breakout topic Architecture specifications, Drivers were asked to review the updated architecture specification. This topic was discussed in the same breakout session as SOPs, since most of the architecture had been validated against the Drivers' requirements in the first installment of the Blueprint validation workshop. Keeping the year 2 updates to the architecture specifications in mind, the Drivers were asked to:

1. **Identify missing elements:** what components, processes, or resources are currently missing?
2. **Identify areas needing refinement:** review existing components that need improvement or clarification
3. **Discuss solutions, gaps, and needs:** are the architecture specifications implementable by each driver or do they see any gaps in implementation?

SOPs

The second year ENTRUST Blueprint is the first version that includes Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs). Therefore, the Drivers were asked to review the included SOPs and validate them against their prototypes (if possible), requirements and the current reality of their partner TREs. The leading questions for the SOPs were the same as for the architecture specifications, namely:

1. **Identify missing elements:** what components, processes, or resources are currently missing?
2. **Identify areas needing refinement:** review existing components that need improvement or clarification
3. **Discuss solutions, gaps, and needs:** are the architecture specifications implementable by each driver or do they see any gaps in implementation?

Legal framework

The final ENTRUST Blueprint is aimed to include template legal agreements. In the second year version of the Blueprint, which was validated in this breakout session, different potential contractual frameworks for a federation were described: the peer-to-peer

agreement model⁸ and the consortium agreement model, as well as existing legal agreements that could potentially serve as templates: the NORTRE consortium agreement and DPA templates from SURF and Dutch municipalities.

Drivers were asked to take an inventory of the legislation that is relevant for that Driver and consequently undertake a gap analysis with the models and templates proposed in the Blueprint. This was structured with the following leading questions:

1. Legal framework inventory for the driver

- a. Relevant legislation for Driver
- b. Which laws and regulations are you applicable for your prototype?

2. Gap analysis with the Blueprint

- a. Did the legal templates align with your institutional or national requirements? Which model aligns best?
- b. What legal constraints / roadblocks do we experience in the driver/prototype that have not been covered in the Blueprint?
- c. Which assumptions are made in the Blueprint that do not match the legislative framework?

3. Summarize the outcomes

An additional important leading question was posed to the Drivers by the Architecture WP before the breakout session, namely: Which of the agreement models (peer-to-peer vs consortium) would be applicable or is currently used by the Driver?

Roles & Common Terminology

Roles were not discussed in a separate section in the second ENTRUST Blueprint, but have led to a lot of discussion within the project, especially terminology around roles. Because discussions around these topics often overlap, they were tackled in a single breakout session with the aim of gaining clarity on the way in which roles and terminology should be defined within a federation, giving the differences between Drivers. The second ENTRUST Blueprint includes a table listing possible roles in a TRE federation and the alternative names that are currently in use at TREs. This table was provided in the template for reference along with the EOSC-ENTRUST glossary (under development) and the following leading questions:

Roles

- 1. Which roles are implemented in your TRE prototype? Which TRE roles are relevant for your driver?

⁸ In the peer-to-peer agreements model each TRE has agreements with all other TREs in the federation, while in the consortium agreement model, there is a single consortium agreement including all partner TREs with DPAs added for each project.

2. How do they align with the Blueprint's definitions? Did you encounter any gaps or challenges in mapping or federating roles across institutions or systems?

Common Terminology

1. Were the Blueprint terms clear and applicable?
2. Did you encounter inconsistencies or ambiguities?
3. What terminology refinements would improve interoperability? Please give concrete proposals.

5.3 Uptake of recommendations on the User Journey

In addition to the gap analysis workshop, a small update to the generic Drivers User Journey was made during the drafting of this report to integrate the recommendations offered by the Architecture WP in the second ENTRUST Blueprint report.

6. Description of work accomplished

6.1 Driver 1: Federated Human Genomics as a catalyst for European TRE provision

6.1.1 Prototype description

Aim

This prototype aims to demonstrate secure and federated execution of genomic analysis workflows across two TREs. The main objective is to validate the deployment and operation of the WP20 Workflow Processing reference implementation in a distributed TRE setting. The prototype runs a shared Variant Calling workflow on aligned reads (BAM files) hosted in different TREs, producing variant calls that can support downstream biomarker analyses in colorectal cancer, using EGA datasets generated within the EOSC4Cancer project. The dataset consists of synthetic colorectal cancer genomes from four simulated patients, based on real CRC mutation profiles from the Pancancer Analysis of Whole Genomes (PCAWG) dataset. For each patient, one healthy sample and two tumor samples at different time points were generated, capturing intra-tumor heterogeneity and tumor evolution through simulated subclonal mixtures. To facilitate rapid use and transfer, only data for selected chromosomes harboring relevant alterations were generated, specifically those containing driver alterations related to the patient's clinical history (e.g., treatment-associated resistance mutations). The dataset can be split into two independent subsets to simulate data being hosted in two different TREs.

Through this setup, the prototype illustrates key capabilities such as: (1) preserving data locality and governance by keeping data within each TRE, (2) interoperable execution via standardised workflow packaging and interfaces, and (3) supporting flexibility by allowing each TRE to manage workflows and outputs in accordance with local policies.

This prototype focuses exclusively on the technical setup required for the workflow execution (analysis) stage, including the federated analysis itself, and therefore directly addresses the challenges associated with this specific part of the process. Demonstrating federated genomic analysis, even at this small scale, is a big advancement. However, it should be noted there are steps of the user journey not being addressed by the prototype, as well as some genomic specific aspects to consider that are not meant to be covered by the prototype. Aspects of Driver 1 that are not covered in the technical prototype include: navigating ethical and legal obligations, discovering relevant datasets, managing very large data volumes, ensuring the use of reproducible and approved workflows, and understanding data provenance, as differences in experimental or analytical protocols can affect result comparability.

Implementation

Driver 1's prototype corresponds to a network of two 'Five Safe TES'⁹ model TREs being developed and deployed under 'WP20 Workflow Processing'. For showcasing the federated analysis capabilities of the infrastructure, the setup is being configured to implement a cross-national variant calling pipeline by executing a common, containerized Variant Calling workflow (nf-core/SAREK, a Nextflow workflow based on GATK4 (Genome Analysis Toolkit)) over aligned reads hosted in separate TREs. The pipeline was set up in line with the Five Safes principles and follows a 'data pooling' analysis federated schema, where outputs from the individual workflows are pooled. Workflow execution is confined to the TREs and outputs, subject to local policy and egress controls, are transferred to a central submission layer to be reachable by the researcher. Participant TREs are TRE-FX¹⁰ (UNOTT) and TRE-BSC (BSC). The prototype design focuses exclusively on the analysis stage, demonstrating the secure and federated execution of workflows across TREs, while preceding and subsequent steps of a real-world genomics workflow are considered out of scope. A synthetic colorectal cancer genomic dataset (EGAD50000000276¹¹) generated within EOSC4Cancer and accessed via EGA was used for testing.

The prototype is under development, and expected to fully cover Driver 1 federated execution requirements by M36 (D21.1). As documented in detail at D20.1¹², the current prototype incorporates all the components to support a lightweight cross-TRE federated execution - *i.e.* a job submission interface, an interoperable communication layer based on GA4GH TES¹³ standard, TRE job controllers, a TES-compliant job executor (Funnel¹⁴), and Egress modules. Ongoing efforts are done towards better addressing genomics analysis specific needs by (a) integrating WfExS¹⁵ as the new prototype's job executor, to securely manage complex genomic workflow runs; (b) incorporating an auditable and FAIR cross-TRE data reference system, particularly relevant when using reference datasets (*i.e.* reference genomes) across TREs and (c) ensuring a more friendly use of RO-Crate profiles for both job preparation and execution provenance.

Some initial results on the future prototype components can already be reported. On one hand, efforts were concentrated on manually executing and validating the variant calling workflow within a TRE environment (BSC TRE), where successful runs were achieved on an HPC (High Performance Computing) system using a SLURM-based queuing environment

⁹ Five Safe TES Weave: https://docs.federated-analytics.ac.uk/five_safes_tes

¹⁰ TRE-FX: <https://trefx.uk/>

¹¹ <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD50000000276>

¹² EOSC-ENTRUST D20.1 Second Deployable Demonstrator of Digital Objects & Workflows, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18299760>

¹³ TES GA4GH TES, Task Execution Service: <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/task-execution-service-tes/>

¹⁴ FUNNEL: <https://github.com/ohsu-comp-bio/funnel>

¹⁵ WfExS: <https://github.com/inab/WfExS-backend>

(SLURM is a widely used open-source workload manager for high-performance computing that schedules and manages jobs and resources on compute clusters). With these tests, WfExS demonstrated its capability to support complex, multi-step genomic workflows with rich run provenance (via ‘Workflow Run RO-Crates’ profiles¹⁶) in network-restricted environments and showed compatibility with TES-driven execution contexts through integration tests.

On the other hand, an RO-Crate Validation Service¹⁷ has been released and it is going to be integrated in the submission layer of the prototype (a) to check metadata completeness upon job submission of ‘Workflow¹⁸ RO-Crates’-based tasks and (b) to prepare and validate executions provenance metadata upon job completion through profiles like ‘Workflow Run RO-Crates’¹⁹ or ‘Five Safes RO-Crates’²⁰, both potentially supporting future semi-automatic governance and egress processes.

Overall, the current implementation establishes a minimal yet functional foundation for federated workflow execution aligned with the objectives of EOSC-ENTRUST, while it is expected to evolve towards a complete and robust standard-driven federated execution framework able to be easily embedded into end-to-end compute services.

Learnings

The Driver 1 prototype provides a number of technical and operational insights related to the federated execution of genomic workflows across TREs. While the prototype is limited in scope and still under development, the work carried out so far allows several observations to be made regarding feasibility, constraints, and areas requiring further refinement.

First, the prototype offers early evidence that federated execution of genomic analysis workflows across TREs is technically achievable using standardised interfaces and containerised workflows, even in heterogeneous and restricted environments. The use of GA4GH TES-based communication, combined with standard workflow descriptions, appears to be a promising approach for supporting cross-TRE analysis while preserving data locality and local governance.

Second, the work highlights the importance of workflow standardisation and clearly defined tooling constraints in federated settings. Relying on pre-defined, containerised workflows helps reduce uncertainty around execution environments and reproducibility. At the same

¹⁶ Workflow Run RO-Crate, <https://www.researchobject.org/workflow-run-crate/profiles/>

¹⁷ RO-Crate Validation Service, <https://github.com/eScienceLab/Cratey-Validator>

¹⁸ Workflow RO-Crate, <https://about.workflowhub.eu/Workflow-RO-Crate/>

¹⁹ Workflow Run RO-Crate, <https://www.researchobject.org/workflow-run-crate/profiles/>

²⁰ Stian Soiland-Reyes, et al. TRE-FX Technical Documentation - Five Safes RO-crate. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10376350>

time, discussions around tooling approval indicate potential friction with established genomics research practices, pointing to the need for transparent and well-scoped approval mechanisms that balance control with usability.

Third, the prototype underlines the role of metadata and provenance as foundational elements for governance and interoperability. The adoption of RO-Crate profiles for workflow packaging and execution provenance, together with the development of an RO-Crate Validation Service, suggests a viable path towards automated checks of metadata completeness and structural consistency at submission and egress points. However, this also makes clear that metadata validation alone is insufficient to guarantee safe data release and must be complemented by additional governance and disclosure control processes.

Fourth, the implementation work brings attention to several genomics-specific considerations that become apparent when moving from abstract architectures to concrete setups. These include the handling of reference datasets, assumptions around data harmonisation prior to analysis, management of intermediate artefacts, and interpretation and release of results. Such aspects are not always explicit in generic architectural descriptions but are critical for realistic genomics use cases.

Finally, the prototype illustrates the implications of focusing on a single stage of the user journey, namely the analysis phase. While this focus enabled targeted progress on federated execution, it also revealed dependencies on upstream and downstream processes, such as project registration, access approval, legal agreements, SOPs, and output release, that cannot be fully assessed within the current scope. These observations directly informed the subsequent gap analysis and highlight the need for end-to-end considerations in future iterations.

Overall, Driver 1 provides practical insights into how federated genomic analysis within TREs might be realised, while also clarifying the technical, governance, and legal aspects that require further development before such approaches can be adopted at scale.

6.1.2 Gap analysis

Architecture specifications

Driver 1's prototype is designed as a technical demonstrator rather than a production system. In addition, it does not cover the full end-to-end architecture envisioned in the Blueprint, as the prototype focuses primarily on the analysis phase of what would, in practice, constitute a complete genomics research project. As a result, certain architectural aspects of the Blueprint cannot be fully validated through this operational setting. Nevertheless, based on this experience, we will provide feedback on the elements that we envision should be covered or taken into account across the full end-to-end use case.

The following missing or insufficiently specified capabilities were identified (grouped by architectural capability area):

- **Data life cycle coverage:** The Blueprint does not fully describe data life cycles associated with concrete user stories, particularly in federated scenarios. This includes data ingestion, processing, intermediate storage, result aggregation, release and/or downloads of data, and off-boarding.
- **Trust network and interoperability:** The Blueprint should have explicit architectural elements describing how trust and interoperability is established and maintained between TREs.
- **Tooling approval:** Clarification is needed on how service providers will approve or veto the use of specific tools within their TREs. This includes defining the criteria, processes, and responsibilities for assessing whether user-requested software or analytical tooling can be deployed and used within a given TRE.
- **Monitoring and operational visibility:** The Blueprint does not specify federation-grade observability (workflow status, failures, resource utilisation, queueing, per-node progress) needed to run and troubleshoot distributed workflows across TREs
- **AAAI completeness.** The Blueprint needs clearer treatment of (1) which subject-related attributes are required for access decisions (e.g., affiliation, ethics approvals), (2) comprehensive logging/auditing of user actions and workflow execution.
- **Output control for federated and intermediate results:** The Blueprint under-specifies how intermediate outputs and aggregated results are governed, checked, and released in federated models, including explicit Statistical Disclosure Control expectations and "where outputs go" on release.
- **Data harmonisation/standardisation prior to analysis:** For genomics, the Blueprint should be explicit that harmonisation steps may be mandatory before running federated pipelines (and where those steps happen, by whom, and with what artefacts retained).
- **Federation model constraints driven by law and risk appetite:** The Blueprint will need patterns for what is and is not permissible across borders, including whether intermediate results can move, or be aggregated individually in each TRE, and what federation models are viable.

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- **End-to-end user journey:** the Blueprint requires a unified service portal (preferably open-source) and consistent processes for discovery, access requests/approvals, training/certification, and agreement handling across multiple TREs.

Another gap identified concerns the intersection of data access and software within the project registration process. A project should be understood as the combination of *users, data, and tools*. Consequently, project registration should not only capture information about the users and the datasets they will access, but also explicitly include the software and tools that will be used to perform the analysis. At present, the architecture specifications seem to focus primarily on the user and the data, without sufficiently considering the analytical tools, which are a key component from both governance and operational perspectives.

SOPs

During the Driver 1 breakout session, a point was raised regarding the level of detail expected in SOPs. There was a general consensus that SOPs are typically meant to describe concrete, step-by-step procedures, whereas in this case they appear to provide only high-level guidance. Rather than attempting to define overly detailed SOPs at Blueprint level, it was suggested that it may be more effective to: (i) offer a **framework** (similar to other EU-wide projects like the Genomics Data Infrastructure D4.2²¹) to support the creation of TRE-specific SOPs; (ii) provide best practices and policy-level guidance; and (iii) include maturity models (e.g. FEGA) and concrete success stories that illustrate what “implementing” the Blueprint ultimately means in practice. This would also support the documentation of policies and real-world implementations across different contexts.

The following policy areas were identified as missing or insufficiently covered:

- **Data life cycle SOPs**, aligned with user stories, including ingestion, processing, output generation, data release, and off-boarding.
- **Tooling approval and veto procedures**, defining how service providers approve or restrict the use of tools, workflows, and software within their TREs.
- **Project registration procedures**, covering the intersection of data access, software approval, and user roles (see the Architecture specifications Section for more details).
- **Security breach response SOPs**, including notification, mitigation, and accountability across federated TREs.
- **Output checking and privacy-preserving procedures**, addressing risks of re-identification, inference, or aggregation attacks before data or results leave a TRE.

²¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14003278>

Legal framework

Inventory of relevant legislation:

The main legal instruments relevant to the Driver include:

- **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**, in particular Article 9 governing the processing of special categories of personal data, such as health and genomic data.
- **European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation**, which is expected to significantly shape secondary use of health data by reducing reliance on consent and introducing harmonised governance mechanisms. Regarding the **interaction with Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs)**, their role and implications in data access requests under the EHDS framework should be clarified.
- **National applicable laws**, which vary across Member States and may include legislation on openness of government activities, health data governance, and data protection authorities' interpretations.
- **Intellectual Property (IP) regulations**, relevant for workflows, derived data, and outputs generated within TREs.

This legal landscape is inherently heterogeneous, especially in cross-border scenarios, and poses challenges for harmonised implementation across multiple TREs.

Agreement models: peer-to-peer vs consortium:

Two main legal agreement models have been discussed for the Driver:

- **Peer-to-peer model**, where individual TREs establish bilateral agreements with each other. While this model may be easier to initiate incrementally, it requires a large number of Data Processing Agreements (DPAs), Data Access Agreements (DAAs), and service agreements, resulting in significant legal and administrative overhead.
- **Consortium agreement model**, where all participating TREs sign a single agreement under common terms and conditions. This model is generally favoured, as it provides consistency, reduces duplication, and facilitates trust-building across the network.

Experience from FEGA shows that both models are legally feasible, but that reaching agreements can be a long and resource-intensive process. In FEGA, collaboration agreements were established between EGA central services²² and each national node, complemented by DPAs (e.g., v1.5²³), DAAs²⁴, and service agreements at the node level.

²² <https://ega-archive.org/about/privacy-notice>

²³ https://ega-archive.org/assets/files/EGA_Data_Processing_Agreement_for_information.pdf

²⁴ <https://ega-archive.org/access/data-access-committee/policy-documentation>

While no major legal roadblocks were encountered, the process took several years to mature.

At present, Driver 1 has not formally adopted either model. The consortium agreement approach is considered the most scalable option, but requires further development, particularly for trans-national scenarios, which are not fully covered by existing draft agreements (e.g. national TRE agreements such as NORTRE).

Gaps and legal roadblocks:

Several legal challenges and gaps have been identified that are not fully addressed in the current Blueprint:

- **Cross-border trust and liability:** Driver 1 aims to enable a network of trusted TREs across multiple countries. This requires legal clarity on responsibilities, liabilities, and accountability when data are processed in a TRE located in a different jurisdiction from the data holder.
- **Off-boarding and exit procedures:** While the Blueprint addresses off-boarding, similar procedures are not well documented in existing initiatives such as FEGA, and practical implementation remains limited.
- **Output checking and release of data:** There is limited consensus and few real-world examples on how to legally and operationally govern genomic analyses' output checks, i.e. deciding what results can leave a TRE and under what conditions. This is identified as a significant blocker.
- **Researcher concerns and usability:** Genomics researchers are often accustomed to downloading and analysing genomic data outside TREs. Therefore, when using TREs, usability challenges and complex approval processes for workflows and outputs raise concerns regarding flexibility, timelines, and scientific autonomy.
- **Lack of harmonisation on data identifiability:** There is no consistent interpretation across countries regarding what genomic data can be considered non-identifying or open. For example, somatic variants may be considered non-identifiable in some jurisdictions, while they may also be treated as potentially identifying in others.
- **Changing roles under EHDS:** In some countries (e.g. Norway), principal investigators currently act as data holders. EHDS introduces a different governance model, requiring changes in roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes, especially as TREs begin to host data beyond health data alone.

Roles

In this prototype, which demonstrates secure and federated execution of genomic workflows across multiple TREs, a minimal but clear role model is required to support

distributed workflow execution while preserving data locality, governance, and accountability.

Based on the prototype design and workshop discussions, and aligned where applicable with GDPR Art. 4²⁵, the following functional roles are essential:

- **Data processor:** Natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller. For example, infrastructures providing storage, access services, or controlled data distribution (e.g. EGA/FEGA, TRE provider).
- **Data controller:** natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law.

Driver 1 acknowledges the importance for data controllers to be trained on the steps needed to greenlight a workflow that a researcher would want to execute on their data. Documentation must be provided by the EOSC-ENTRUST project on recommendations against data re-identification.

In most cases, a sub-role of the data controller will also be:

- **Data Access Committee (DAC):** one or more individuals (data controllers) responsible for: (1) evaluating data access requests; (2) managing Data Access Agreements (DAAs); and (3) making access decisions on behalf of Data Controllers. The members of a DAC should be individuals who have the authority to approve data access requests.
- **Health Data Access Bodies / Secondary Use Controllers:** A mandatory, government-designated authority in each EU Member State responsible for managing, approving, and facilitating secure access to electronic health data for secondary use (e.g., research, policy) under the European Health Data Space (EHDS).

It can be seen as an EU-member overarching-type of DAC.

Particularly relevant in the context of EHDS, these roles are expected to become increasingly important and should be explicitly considered in the role model, even if not directly exercised in this prototype.

²⁵ <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-4-gdpr>

The following roles are encompassed by either data processor or data controller, in possible varied combinations:

- **Data submitter:** The actor responsible for submitting data.
- **Data users / Researchers:** The authorised individual executing workflows and analysing data within the TRE.

Note that a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body may have, simultaneously, multiple of the above defined roles. Combinations of roles are possible in the life-cycle of the data.

For example, a data submitter may also be the data controller, but it could be that the data submitter is a different entity than the data controller, making them a data processor processing the data (submitting it to an archive/TRE) on behalf of the data controller.

The workshop highlighted that some roles and terminology are inconsistently defined and dispersed across the Blueprint, glossary, and diagrams, with missing or overlapping definitions (e.g. data custodian mixed with data controller), and in particular an ambiguous use of “Data Provider” that blurs institutional controllers with data holders, originators, or even data subjects, conflicting with established EGA/FEGA practice.

A specific concern raised for the genomics domain relates to researcher expectations and established working practices. Genomics researchers are accustomed to highly flexible environments, including the ability to bring their own tools, access external resources, and iteratively develop and adapt workflows. If tools or workflows are subject to restrictive approval processes or vetoed without clear justification, this can significantly hinder research productivity and user acceptance. Any governance or control mechanisms introduced in TREs therefore need to carefully balance security and compliance requirements with sufficient flexibility to support effective genomic research.

Finally, we would like to stress that roles need to be clearly defined and consistently matched to the applicable legal frameworks, such as GDPR, EHDS, and other relevant regulations.

Terminology

As explained in the Roles section, we felt that both the glossary and roles are split and mixed: some definitions are missing, and roles need to be defined concisely in the glossary. In addition, there are inconsistencies between the diagrams and the glossary, making it difficult to have a clear and aligned understanding. The Blueprint and the glossary should therefore be more extensive and aligned, providing concrete definitions that can accommodate differences across domains and countries. For example, the Blueprint uses

“Data User/TRE User,” SATRE uses “Data Consumer/Data Analyst,” while Driver 1 genomics TREs typically refer to “Researcher,” “Authorised User,” or “Applicant.”

6.1.3 Summary of gaps

Topic	Gap(s)
Architecture specifications	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Missing intermediary storage definition/regulation, needed for multi-step workflow execution.• Minimal disclosure procedure (a baseline mechanism/process for disclosure control prior to egress)• Federation trust and interoperability mechanics are not specified at an operationally actionable level for Driver 1.• Tooling approval/veto and "project = users + data + tools": Driver 1 needs the architecture to explicitly represent how tool/workflow requests are assessed and authorised per TRE, and how this is captured in project registration (not just users and datasets).• End-to-end data lifecycle patterns for federated genomics (e.g., ingestion, intermediate artefacts, result aggregation, release/download, off-boarding).
SOPs	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Missing SOP framework to generate consistent EOSC-ENTRUST SOPs. Similar to the European Genomic Data Infrastructure D4.2²⁶.• Blueprint-level SOPs are not yet provided: D14.1²⁷ states future Blueprint versions will add operating procedures (and interfaces), implying SOP-level guidance is currently incomplete for federation.• Data lifecycle SOPs aligned to concrete federated user stories (ingestion → processing → output generation → release → off-boarding).• Tool/workflow approval SOPs (e.g., criteria, responsibilities, escalation, turnaround times; including provider veto conditions). Also important to note the relevance of internet access for Driver 1, and how it would be regulated within TREs, if allowed.• Project registration SOPs that explicitly include requested tools/workflows alongside users and datasets, and link to

²⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14003278>

²⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15608124>

	<p>approval gates.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Security incident/breach response SOPs that work across federated TREs (notification, mitigation, accountability).● Output checking/disclosure control SOPs (privacy-preserving checks against re-identification/inference/aggregation risks before egress), especially important for genomics outputs.
Legal framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● HDAB interplay (how access requests and roles change under EHDS where applicable).● Template legal agreements for federation to ease collaboration and maintain consistency.● Cross-border responsibility/liability model for processing in another jurisdiction (e.g., DPAs).● Legal-operational governance of output checking and release remains a major blocker (who decides, under what conditions, what logs/evidence are required). This includes intellectual property regulations.● Harmonisation of "identifiability" interpretations for genomics (what can be considered non-identifying) remains inconsistent across jurisdictions. GDPR Recital 26²⁸ vaguely refers to ‘means reasonably likely to be used’, which is even more complex for Driver 1 (e.g., genomic markers, transcriptomic profiles).● Off-boarding/exit enforceability (timely deletion, retention, auditability).
Roles	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Federation governance roles and responsibilities are not fully defined for Driver 1 to implement consistently.● DACs as first-class roles: critical in genomics access governance, but not clearly treated as a primary role in the Blueprint role model.● Principal Investigator (PI) role vs governance roles: Driver 1 still needs the roles of “PI” and “input/output approver” reconciled with genomics practice (e.g. DAC-led decisions, controller responsibilities).● Clear mapping of roles to legal frameworks (GDPR, EHDS) for cross-border processing (e.g., who is the controller/processor in

²⁸ <https://gdpr-info.eu/recitals/no-26>

	workflow executions).
Terminology	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Standardised terminology is not yet complete. Similar to “SPE and TRE terminology for sensitive data processing”²⁹, a common (EOSC-ENTRUST-wide) charter, glossary and definitions are needed.• Role and term collisions across artefacts (glossary vs diagrams vs domain usage) remain problematic for Driver 1.

6.2 Driver 2: Common standards to enable trans-national sharing of administrative and social science data

6.2.1 Prototype description

The partners in Driver 2 are from three data services: two have established TREs (UKDS (UK) and GESIS (Germany)) and the third one is still at the planning stage for a TRE (TARKI, Hungary). In Driver 2, unlike in most of the other Drivers, the TREs are positioned within data archives. This means the data are owned by the research center/survey team responsible for managing the data collection but held within the GESIS or UKDS data archives. This way, the data owners don't directly make the data available to users – the access is handled by the archives via their TREs.

To develop a suitable prototype, we considered a scenario that is hypothetical but not unusual in practice. We hypothesise that three researchers want to access social media data held by GESIS in Germany. The researchers are based in Germany, the UK, and Hungary. To access the data, the process is currently as follows. All researchers must complete the application process at GESIS, and following that, all must, in theory, travel to Cologne to access the data via the GESIS Safe Room. There is an existing remote desktop connection to GESIS at the UKDS' Safe Room (set up during the [SSHOC project](#)), so the UK researcher could potentially travel to the UKDS Safe Room to access the data from there. However, there is no option for the researcher in Hungary but to travel to Germany.

An important step forward and towards being able to facilitate federated analysis across borders is the ability to move data to a different Secure Environment for the duration and purpose of a research project. This has not been possible for any of the Driver 2 partners previously.

²⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15696511>

We have piloted the move of data into a third-party secure environment and tested the potential for federation. For our pilot prototype, we have used an existing system, so far available only in the Netherlands, namely the SANE Secure ANalysis Environment³⁰ developed by SURF³¹. The SANE system provides a virtual, fully-shielded computing environment for access to sensitive data, and runs on the ISO-27001 certified SURF Research Cloud. SANE is developed by SURF and the partners of ODISSEI³² (Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations), [National Library of the Netherlands \(KB\)](#), [Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision \(NISV\)](#), and [CLARIAH](#) (Common Lab Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities). Two variants of SANE are currently available: ‘Tinker’ and ‘Blind’. With Tinker SANE, the researcher is presented with a virtual desktop to see and manipulate the data. It is not possible to transfer the data outside the Tinker environment. Blind SANE offers a remote execution option, whereby the researcher can submit a non-interactive analysis that will be executed using the sensitive data in a controlled environment, without the ability to see the data. The analysis can be either a script or a Docker container. For either variant, researchers can log into the secure SANE network, irrespective of location.

Using SANE for the Driver 2 prototype has allowed us to test whether we can ease the journey to gaining access to sensitive data held in a different country as a significant step towards federation.

Overall, we have used the SANE prototype system to learn which of the main challenges faced when setting up/using TREs across borders can be eased. For example:

- We hope to ease some policy/legal constraints where data transfer across borders has not been an option for secure-access data, and cross-national access has so far only been enabled by remote desktop access between Safe Rooms. The risk appetite of data owners is a limiting/prohibitive factor. With that in mind, can the inherent security of the third-party system help to overcome this barrier?
- Equivalence issues usually arise also regarding technical requirements of the secure environment. This is crucial for getting different TREs/countries to agree to data sharing and moving data into another secure environment. In the 5 Safes Framework, which enables many TREs in the UK to make secure access data available to researchers, ‘Secure Setting’ is one of the 5 Safes of that framework. How far will having a central, third-party infrastructure help abate concerns?
- Resource constraints are an issue for many organisations; for example, limited funding and/or a scarcity of trained professionals to set up and maintain TREs can

³⁰

<https://www.surf.nl/en/themes/research-infrastructure/sane-secure-environment-for-analysing-sensitive-data>

³¹ <https://www.surf.nl/en>

³² <https://odissei-data.nl/nl/>

be prohibitive. How can adopting a third-party infrastructure help overcome limited resources?

The GESIS-SANE and UKDS-SANE pilots

	GESIS-SANE Pilot	UKDS-SANE Pilot
Duration	15 September – 15 November 2025	21 October 2025 – 28 February 2026
Testing	Tinker SANE	1) Tinker SANE and 2) Blind SANE
Data	Bespoke dataset with web-tracking data	<p>Four Controlled ‘Next Steps’ (also known as the Longitudinal Study of Young People in England (LSYPE1)) datasets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ●8656 Next Steps: Sweeps 1-8, 2004-2016: Secure Access ●8190 Next Steps: Sweep 8, 2016: Geographical Identifiers, 2011 Census Boundaries: Secure Access ●8189 Next Steps: Sweeps 1 and 8, 2001 and 2016: Geographical Identifiers, 2001 Census Boundaries: Secure Access ●9337 Next Steps: Sweep 9, 2022: Geographical Identifiers, 2021 Census Boundaries: Secure Access <p>Alongside the Controlled Data we also imported the ONS 2021 Rural–Urban Classification (RUC) of LSOAs for England and Wales, which is available under standard Open Government Licence terms.</p>

Third-party infrastructure	The Secure ANalysis Environment (SANE), provided and operated by SURF (Netherlands, EEA)	The Secure ANalysis Environment (SANE), provided and operated by SURF (Netherlands, EEA)
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The GESIS-SANE pilot had 4 core objectives:

- 1) To test the use of a third party infrastructure to enable our existing TRE to pivot from on-site and remote access to remote desktop access as a small service with limited resources.
- 2) To test the use of a third party infrastructure to expand our technical capacities, both in terms of computational capacity and of statistical software available. This is an important strategic goal to enable us to meet growing needs for newer forms of big datasets and unstructured datasets.
- 3) Tinker SANE: verify that researchers both within Germany and across Europe can log in and run analyses interactively in the locked-down desktop within SANE.
- 4) To test whether adopting SANE enables us as a smaller TRE to meet the requirements of both the research community (data input, analysis, output release, etc.) and the requirements for joining the ENTRUST network of TREs (as set out in the Blueprint).

The GESIS-SANE pilot was completed in November 2025 and was considered to have successfully fulfilled our core objectives. Moving on from the pilot, work has continued to formally adopt the SANE infrastructure on a temporary basis to allow us to offer remote desktop access for the first time to our research community, and to allow us to offer a better working environment for researchers with the capacity to work with additional software such as Python, and to work with large, unstructured datasets.

The UKDS-SANE Pilot had 5 objectives:

- 1) Provider-managed data ingress and project provisioning: explore how the UK Data Service (UKDS), as Data Service Provider, can (a) lawfully transfer/ingress the licensed real Controlled Data into SANE; and (b) provision a test project/workspace with correct role-based access controls for a named user.
- 2) Tinker SANE: verify that non-UK researchers can log in, run analyses interactively in the locked-down desktop, and manage working files within SANE.
- 3) Blind SANE: verify researchers/peer reviewers can execute (submitted) code without data visibility, retrieve logs, and validate that outputs reflect correct execution while preventing data exposure.
- 4) External documentation/data import (in principle): test the procedural and technical pathway for provider-approved import of external reference files needed to run code

(e.g., look-up tables, codebooks, package whitelists), as well as import of data files for linkages.

- 5) Output checks (in principle): exercise the end-to-end Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) request-and-review flow for sample outputs, confirming process and audit trails.

We have started the pilot on 21st October 2025, and the pilot is, at the time of writing this report, still ongoing. UKDS-SANE will be finalised by the end of February 2026. However, we are able to report that, so far, objectives 1, 2, and 4 have been tested successfully, and objectives 3 and 5 will be tested until the end of the UKDS-SANE pilot.

In addition to the two SANE pilots, a report is being compiled by the third Driver 2 partner TARKI. TARKI represents a data service right at the beginning of its journey to becoming a TRE, and its report aims to evaluate TARKI's current capability to satisfy the specified requirements outlined in the Blueprint. It summarises each requirement from the previously accepted Blueprint report, presents assessment results for a service without an existing TRE – using TARKI's current state as an example service – along with guidance on how to meet those requirements. The report also includes cost estimations for implementing the technical requirements, documentation and specifications of all requirements necessary for a successful integration into the EOSC Federation, and an action plan incorporating risk assessment and mitigation strategies to achieve full compliance. TARKI's draft report will be due in October 2026, and the final report in January 2027.

6.2.2 Gap analysis

Architecture specifications

In terms of the architecture specifications outlined in the Blueprint, many of the gaps were previously identified in the [D7.1 Driver Validation report](#) and partially addressed afterwards. At this stage, a few additional architectural gaps and refinements were identified:

Certification Process for TREs joining the federation

Thought should be given to whether fully centralised certification is practical given the variation in the Drivers' requirements, or whether a decentralised certification process would be required with mechanisms for onboarding criteria and mutual trust building. The Blueprint should then set out the mode of certification more clearly.

Training for researchers and TRE staff

Although the requirement for safe researcher training was previously discussed, it is

reiterated here that this and training for TRE staff at level that the federation accepts must be included, and to ease the process, this training should be recorded in a Researcher Passport or other such electronic training record which should ideally have the capacity to link with the AAI.

SOPs

In terms of the SOPs, the needs of individual TREs will vary across services, across countries and across disciplinary borders. To this aim, SOPs at the TRE level need to be far more detailed than those in the Blueprint (which might stay at the policy level, as Driver 1 also suggested). Therefore we propose that the Blueprint should focus on federation-level SOPs that enable consistent ways of working across participating TREs. To support this, it would be useful to define a minimal set of recommended and/or mandatory SOPs required to establish a functional TRE federation, alongside templates or a lightweight framework that would accelerate drafting and finalisation within TRE federations. At this time, Driver 2 will not establish new SOPs at the TRE level, since GESIS and UKDS have well-established TRE-level SOPs in place that are being followed.

For Driver 2, the following SOPs are missing from the Blueprint:

Federation onboarding and certification process

SOPs are required to set out the requirements for TREs joining the federation. Careful consideration would be needed for how these enable the building of trust and mutual recognition of standards between TREs.

Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) rules/processes

It is not practical to have a standardised set of statistical disclosure rules across the federation, as the exact rules will vary by data type, level of sensitivity, etc. However, SOPs which set out the requirement for statistical disclosure rules that are equivalent across the federation are needed. The Blueprint should also recognise the need to consider complex output scenarios such as output requests where projects have used data from multiple TREs/providers. Here, clear guidelines should set out a solution for coordinating SDC in these cases.

Data identification and citation

SOPs should be set at the federation level to ensure there are mechanisms in place to allow data to be properly cited (i.e. the availability of a persistent identifier for datasets such as a DOI).

Archiving and data withdrawal policies

Common SOPs should be provided for the long term archival of projects that take into account the varying legal requirements for different countries/TREs, specifying what should

be archived and where and for how long. Consideration should also be given to implementing a 'red button' mechanism for data withdrawal.

Breach handling policy

Broad SOPs should be available at the federation level on how data breaches should be handled. Minor procedural breaches would remain the remit of individual TREs, but where data confidentiality or infrastructure security has been breached, or legislative action ensues, consideration should be given to setting up a centralised Information Security Management Group that would be responsible for investigation and handling of these more serious breaches. SOPs should include an agreement that where sanctions have been applied, all federation partners are informed.

Current SOPs that require refinement:

Centralised software provision

This is partially considered, but some additional detail is required to set how the available software and packages are regularly updated, and how versioning is managed, and by whom.

User Support

The Blueprint sets out different levels of support, however this may not be practical in reality, especially where TREs have very small teams. Regardless, support teams at the federation level will be required to action (receive and distribute) federated requests and coordinate signing off of multiple data use agreements, put together ad-hoc DACs etc.

Legal framework

Responsibility & control vary in individual agreements between data controllers and researchers

Data sharing is typically governed by project-specific, peer-to-peer agreements between institutions and researchers. However, the allocation of responsibility and liability differs across national frameworks. Under GDPR, institutions usually act as data controllers, but this is not universally permitted or interpreted, creating uncertainty around accountability and researcher protection.

National frameworks are necessary in addition to GDPR for sensitive data sharing

GDPR, particularly Articles 6 and 9, is the main legal basis for sensitive data processing, but national legislation and sector-specific frameworks also apply. EHDS influences terminology and requirements for health data, and differences between EU and UK GDPR must be considered in cross-border contexts.

Clarification in output control and responsibility for outputs in agreements

Many agreements focus on data access but insufficiently address responsibility for research outputs, such as publications or derived results. This is especially relevant in federated or “data-stays-at-source” models, where roles and accountability for outputs are less clear.

Legal & technical challenges of software licensing and infrastructure governance

Federated analysis environments introduce unresolved issues around software licensing, as vendors often lack models suitable for cross-institutional or federated use. License management across jurisdictions adds another layer of contractual and compliance complexity.

Peer-to-peer vs consortium agreement models – what is the current status and what is feasible for the Driver to implement.

Peer-to-peer is current practice, but consortium agreements have advantages. Bilateral agreements are widely used but become administratively burdensome at scale, particularly for intermediary organizations. Consortium agreements can provide a shared legal foundation for large or long-term federations, reducing overhead, while still allowing for project-specific data access agreements.

Where the agreements include data transfer into a third party infrastructure, consideration should be given to potential data ownership issues. Data ownership and control depend on both national law and data origin. In some jurisdictions, institutions – not individual researchers – own data collected in research. When data is provided by third parties, ownership and decision-making often remain with the original data holder, complicating consent, reuse, and responsibility.

Legal constraints or roadblocks that are not covered in the Blueprint:

Terminology misalignment is a major barrier to interoperability

Terms such as *data controller*, *data processor*, *data holder*, and *data owner* are defined and applied differently across institutions, countries, and frameworks (GDPR vs. EHDS). The Blueprint’s assumption of uniform terminology does not hold in practice, leading to confusion, legal risk, and difficulties in aligning templates across borders.

Complex consent and opt-out mechanisms

Consent, particularly for non-health personal data, is not uniformly regulated or harmonized across jurisdictions. The Blueprint assumes relatively straightforward consent and opt-out mechanisms, but participants emphasized that actual legislative requirements are often more restrictive or incompatible, especially when combining GDPR, EHDS, and national

laws. In addition, the GDPR sets out a number of legal gateways through which data can be made available for research. The particular gateway used will determine to some degree the SOPs for processing and approving applications.

Legal and historical constraints for the standardization of agreements

While standardized templates are desirable, legacy agreements (such as contracts restricting access to physical locations) and historical institutional practices can conflict with modern federated or remote access models. How to overcome these constraints needs to be considered.

Foundational data processing agreements as a prerequisite for data access agreements

A clear distinction must be maintained between data processing agreements (between legal entities as required under GDPR) and data access agreements (project- or researcher-specific). Processing agreements must be established first, yet this foundational step is often underestimated in terms of effort and complexity.

Legal and business clarity for long-term data retention and sustainability

Data retention periods can extend up to several decades, raising questions about long-term storage responsibilities, costs, and business models for data spaces. These considerations intersect with legal obligations under GDPR and national law but are not yet fully integrated into agreement frameworks. Where data retention and storage is handled at the federation level, consideration is needed of the impact that combined datasets have on their legal status.

Roles & Terminology

Alignment or gaps with the Blueprint role definitions

Fine-tuning is needed in several places, e.g. regarding the following points.

- For the UKDS and GESIS, a PI would not be the 'Input approver' and 'Output approver', the PI would rather be the import requester and output requester. The 'Data processor' would be the checker for imports and outputs (including SDC checks).
- It is very important regarding output/SDC checks how these will have to be done - based on the four eyes principle or (semi)automated, according to which SDC rules, and by whom? Further, would the above be defined in the Consortium Agreement of the EOSC Federation or in Peer-to-Peer Agreements?
- The terms 'data holder' and 'data controller' need to be very clearly defined, maybe in alignment with the EHDS terminology?
- A crucial point will be the question of the software. Will software be provided or brought to the secure environment or partially provided (which) and partially brought to it? The 'software approver' role very much depends on how that aspect will be designed. Is there one entity federation-wide? Who pays for licences, the

hosting entity or the researcher or the data provider or all of them (and to what percentages)?

- The ‘job approver’ role would have to be split into two.
- It would need to be defined which role in the federation would be responsible for the researcher training (and test?) prior to being granted access to the data.
- One main difference between UKDS and GESIS is the distinction between ‘data holder’ and ‘data owner’ (the latter is not an extra category in the current architecture). Further, ‘data holder’ and ‘TRE governance’ are one entity in some places.

Alignment or gaps in applicability of terminology from Glossary to Driver

It would be good to see some amendments to the Glossary. One term, we would, for example, like to see added and clearly defined, is a ‘project’.

6.2.3 Summary of gaps

Topic	Gap(s)
Architecture specifications & SOPs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Certification Process of TREs joining the federation ● Training for researchers and TRE staff ● Federation onboarding and certification process ● Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) rules/processes ● Data identification and citation ● Archiving and Data Withdrawal policies ● Breach handling policy ● Centralised software provision ● User Support
Legal framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Responsibility and control vary in individual agreements between data controllers and researchers ● National frameworks are necessary in addition to GDPR for sensitive data sharing ● Clarification in output control and responsibility for outputs in agreements

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Legal & technical challenges of software licensing and infrastructure governance
Roles & Terminology	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Project• Data holder/data owner• Input approver/ output approver• Software approver• Job approver• Alignment with EHDS terminology

6.3 Driver 3: Enabling the re-use of clinical trials data for research purposes across Europe

6.3.1 Prototype description

The Driver 3 prototype is entitled “*Federated analysis of Randomized Controlled Trial and Real-World data across two Trusted Research Environments to compare comorbidities in older adults vaccinated against COVID-19*”.

The objective of the prototype is twofold:

- i) To investigate analytical approaches for federating two TREs, operating in two different countries (TSD³³ in Norway and HIC³⁴ in Scotland), for an analysis involving two different data types (Randomized Controlled Trial – RCT and Real World Data – RWD).
- ii) To perform an evidence synthesis comparing Individual Participant Data (IPD) from an RCT with RWD filtered by similar inclusion criteria to assess the generalizability of the trial results on comorbidities in elderly individuals vaccinated against COVID-19.

Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT)

- *Study*: Assessing Immune Response of Different COVID-19 Vaccines in Older Adults (EU-COVAT-1) (NCT05160766)³⁵
- *Data controller*: University of Cologne
- *Data source*: crDSR³⁶ (TSD TRE in Norway)
- *Population*: 269 participants
- *Metadata*: Documented in crDSR³⁷

Real-World Data (RWD)

- *Data controller*: National Health Service (NHS) Tayside, Scotland
- *Data source*: Vaccination records of the Tayside population stored in HIC TRE in Scotland
- *Population*: 411,643 individuals
- *Metadata*: Documented in Healthdatagateway³⁸

³³ <https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/>

³⁴ <https://www.dundee.ac.uk/hic>

³⁵ Neuhann JM, Stemler J, Carcas AJ, Frías-Iniesta J. et al. Immunogenicity and reactogenicity of a first booster with BNT162b2 or full-dose mRNA-1273: A randomised VACCCELERATE trial in adults ≥75 years (EU-COVAT-1). *Vaccine*. 2023;41(48):7166-7175. doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2023.10.029.

³⁶ <https://crdsr.ecriin.org/login>

³⁷ <https://crdsr.ecriin.org/browsing/studies/DSRS-2/view>

³⁸ <https://healthdatagateway.org/en/data-custodian/10>

The “lessons learned” of this prototype study seeking to analyse baseline characteristics, vaccination and comorbidity data held by two TREs feeds into the process of defining requirements for TRE federation in EOSC-ENTRUST. This is done by evaluating the feasibility and applicability of the analytical models below. Applying in practice some of the models is challenging (or even impossible due to TRE governance requirements) but an important outcome of our prototype involves documenting when a specific model cannot be applied, what the reasons are and which changes may be needed to enable analysis.

Model no	Analysis type	Description	Our prototype
1	2-stage	Datasets are analysed in the TRE holding them. The aggregated (and anonymous) results of the individual studies are collected and combined outside of the TREs.	IPD analysed separately in the TSD TRE and the HIC TRE. Aggregated results combined outside of the TREs. Disclosure risk mitigation will be taken into consideration.
2	Data pooling	Aggregate results from individual studies (analyzed in TREs) are pooled in a TRE within a federated network.	IPD analysed separately in the TSD TRE and the HIC TRE. Aggregated results combined in one of the two TREs. Disclosure risk mitigation will be taken into consideration.
3	Remote execution (simple)	A single TRE provides a view of IPD from multiple studies in the federated network, allowing the researcher to view and interact with the data. A virtual table is created from different sources, but full analysis depends on the capabilities of the presenting tool. It’s up to the hosting TRE (and project governance) to decide what the researcher can and can’t do. Model 3 is a simpler version of Model 4, and it is useful when remote queries can be easily encapsulated in a single message and datasets are homogeneous and tabular.	TSD and HIC are not yet part of a federated TRE network. In a theoretical exercise, requirements for Model 3 are being collected.

4	Remote execution (generic)	<p>The analysis is executed in one TRE, but it accesses IPD stored in multiple external TREs within the federated network. More advanced than Model 3, allowing complex multi-study analyses without direct data movement.</p> <p>The main difference between Model 3 and Model 4 comes down to the complexity of the query sent between TREs. Model 3 works with simple queries that can be directly sent from TRE A to TRE B, while Model 4 handles more complex queries that can't be packaged as a simple message. Instead, TRE A asks TRE B to run a specific workflow provided by a third-party service (e.g. Software Service C). Thus Model 4 adds an extra layer by involving a third party to handle complex workflows, while Model 3 relies on straightforward, direct queries.</p>	<p>TSD and HIC are not yet part of a federated TRE network.</p> <p>In a theoretical exercise, requirements for Model 4 are being collected.</p>
5	1-stage	<p>IPD of all data sources are available and accessible in one TRE. The analysis is performed in this TRE. Data transfer(s) are needed.</p>	<p>In a theoretical exercise, requirements for Model 5 are being collected.</p>

To better evaluate the capacity of the two TREs involved in Driver 3 a point-by-point comparison of their capacities has been provided³⁹.

The protocol of the study is publicly available in Zenodo⁴⁰.

Current status and next steps for the prototype:

- Study protocol finalised with input from ECRIN, UNIVDUN and UiO.

³⁹ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1TLuMy0iedlOXMa-TwkjmCX64TABjLoDu/edit>

⁴⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/17431505>

- Approval of the protocol by the responsible data access committees (according to the crDSR and HIC policies). Registration of the study protocol in Zenodo.
- Data access request in the TREs (crDSR, HIC), including user training (when needed) and signature of data use/access agreements.
- Data analysts have received logins and access to both datasets in the crDSR and HIC.
- Statistical analysis of IPD to assess the generalisability of the RCT results and evaluate feasibility of the different TRE analytical models (January–March 2026).
- Summary of the results in a public report and input of the study results into the requirements elucidation process for the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint (April–June 2026).

6.3.2 Gap analysis

Architecture specifications

Missing capability

- *Federation Rulebook artifact*
Add a Federation Rulebook as an explicit governance artifact, owned by the Federation Governance, capturing common policies, operational rules, and compliance requirements for all federation participants.

Capabilities to refine

Federation Services/Registries

- Clarify the relationship between Projects and Agreements in Federation Services/Registries: whether a Project is a container grouping multiple Agreements, and whether Agreements can exist outside a Project context.
- Refine the Project definition to state if it is primarily an authorisation context (access scope, data usage context) and/or a funding construct, and ensure the architecture is explicit about this choice.

Job Submission Service

- Refine the Job Submission Service capability to distinguish between:
 - a job submission interface operated inside a federated TRE/RAZ/Processing Environment, and
 - a job submission interface exposed to “outside-the-federation” clients.
- Extend the capability description to cover:
 - handling and governance of outputs/results (validation before release, disclosure control, “data damage” prevention);
 - mandatory script/query validation workflows and data manager approval steps;
 - an assessment of TRE readiness to host such job submission services.

Software Services

- Refine Software Services to specify whether they manage:
 - research user-facing software environments (tools, workflows, containers),
 - the TRE's own platform software,
 - or both, with clear separation of concerns.
- Clarify whether Software Services are user-facing, back-end, or hybrid, and whether adjacent services (data quality, workflow registries, terminology services) are part of this capability or modelled as separate specialized services (e.g. Terminology Service, Data Quality Service, Workflow/Tool Registry integrated with GitHub/WorkflowHub-like resources).

Indexing and linking services

- Separate Index Services (creation and maintenance of linkage identifiers/spines) from Linking Services (operational data linkage that uses those spines), acknowledging that they can be operated by different roles and at different places in the federation.
- Refine the description so that linkage spines are produced without exposing detailed source datasets to index operators, and data linkers can “zip” datasets together without learning unnecessary details from each side, supporting privacy-preserving linkage patterns.

SOPs

Driver 3 will not establish new SOPs at TRE level, since TSD and HIC already have TRE-level SOPs in place and these are being followed. The Blueprint should focus on **federation-level SOPs** that enable consistent ways of working across participating TREs.

To support this, it would be useful to define **a minimal set of recommended and/or mandatory SOPs** required to establish a functional TRE federation, alongside **templates** or **a lightweight framework** that would accelerate drafting and finalisation within TRE federations.

Legal framework

Relevant legislation inventory for Driver 3

- **GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679)**

The Driver 3 prototype data processing activity needs a lawful basis. **Consent** is the legal basis for the clinical trial data and “**task carried out in the public interest / official authority**” (GDPR Art. 6(1)(a) and Art. 6(1)(e)) is the legal basis for the routinely collected healthcare data.

Peer-to-peer vs consortium agreement model

- Peer-to-peer, fully bilateral contracting is perceived by Driver 3 partners as complex to scale and difficult to govern consistently for high-sensitivity health data.
- Feedback from existing TRE networks (e.g. national TRE collaborations) demonstrates a clear preference of current TRE collaborations towards Consortium Agreements.

Additional legal constraints for the Blueprint

- The Blueprint does not fully cover that **indirect, “eyes-off” access** is, to the best of our knowledge, still considered personal data processing and thus requires a full GDPR-compliant legal basis and Data Access Agreement. Additional guidance could focus on clarifying whether federation-level agreements can provide a blanket legal umbrella for indirect access patterns, and how to reflect this in ethics approvals and information notices.
- The Blueprint **under-specifies breach notification in federated, multi-country projects**. It would be of added value to reflect upon the chain of responsibility and notification in projects involving multiple TREs. EOSC-ENTRUST needs a shared responsibility model and standardized breach handling clauses embedded in the federation Consortium Agreement and downstream DPAs.
- The Blueprint tends to treat TREs in a single legal role, while within Driver 3 it was raised that TREs can act as Data Controllers, Joint Controllers or Data Processors. This **flexibility of role assignment for TREs** should be reflected in the Blueprint’s architectural and legal specifications.

Roles

Both TREs in Driver 3 (TSD and HIC) identified four main role categories:

- **Federation governance roles:** Oversee the federated infrastructure and cross-TRE operations
- **TRE governance roles:** Manage individual TRE instances and their operations
- **Data user roles:** Enable researchers and analysts to access and work with data
- **Data provider roles:** Facilitate data contribution and management

Some considerations for the Blueprint:

- Change Data Controller from a fixed actor to a role that can be assumed by different entities depending on dataset, jurisdiction, and Agreement, and update role-actor mappings accordingly.
- Introduce a Data Access Committee role/capability responsible for reviewing and approving data access requests under the Federation Rulebook and specific Agreements.

- **Federation Services Operators:** These operators manage the technical infrastructure enabling federation across TREs. They are currently missing from the diagram in the 2nd version of the Blueprint and need to be incorporated under federation governance.
- **Input Approver:** This role focuses on data approval rather than software validation. Driver 3 suggests creating a separate **Software Approver role** within TRE governance to handle software validation and approval processes.
- **Output Control roles:** Output control responsibilities must be defined at the federation level, particularly for federated analyses spanning multiple TREs. Potentially consider adding a **“Lead TRE” role** that would coordinate output control across federated analysis projects.
- **Training roles:** The TRE Operator role can cover training activities and user support provision, though these responsibilities require explicit clarification in the Blueprint text. Driver 3 suggestion is that **training and user support are provided both at TRE governance and federation governance level.**

Terminology

General recommendations

- *Separate abbreviations and definitions*

Maintain distinct lists for abbreviations (acronyms and short forms) and for terminology (concepts and their definitions).

- *Adopt recognised external definitions*

Whenever possible, reuse authoritative definitions from established sources rather than creating new ones.

- Legal terms such as data controller or pseudonymisation should adopt definitions from EU data protection law (e.g., GDPR and EDPS glossary).
- Domain-specific terms should align with relevant external glossaries, such as:
DSSC’s “Key Concepts of Data Spaces”⁴¹
UK Trusted Research Environment (TRE) Glossary⁴²

- *Avoid redefinition without real necessity*

When a suitable definition already exists, use it as-is unless there is a strong need to adapt it to the project’s specific context. In such cases, any modifications should be clearly justified and documented.

- *Build a harmonised EOSC-ENTRUST glossary*

⁴¹

<https://dssc.eu/space/BVE2/1071251613/Introduction+-+Key+Concepts+of+Data+Spaces#2.1-Participants>

⁴² <https://glossary.uktre.org/en/latest/>

Currently we observe that terminology differs across project documents. Developing a shared EOSC-ENTRUST glossary would be very valuable. The implementation steps could be:

- Step 1: Consolidate all terms and abbreviations into a single, shared spreadsheet (initial working version).
- Step 2: Store the spreadsheet in a clearly accessible location (e.g., shared project drive or repository) and communicate its location to all contributors.
- Step 3: Establish a lightweight process for proposing new terms or revisions, encouraging community validation and traceability.

6.3.3 Summary of gaps

Topic	Gap(s)
Architecture specifications	<p>A Federation Rulebook, capturing common policies, operational rules, and compliance requirements for all federation participants, needs to be provided.</p> <p>Define “Project” and clarify if it is primarily an authorisation context (access scope, data usage context) and/or a funding construct.</p> <p>Refine Software Services to specify whether they manage:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - research user-facing software environments (tools, workflows, containers) - the TRE’s own platform software - or both, with clear separation of concerns. <p>Refine the Job Submission Service capability to distinguish between</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - a job submission interface operated inside a federated TRE/RAZ/Processing Environment, and - a job submission interface exposed to “outside-the-federation” clients. <p>Separate Index Services (creation and maintenance of linkage identifiers/spines) from Linking Services (operational data linkage that uses those spines).</p>

SOPs	Define a minimal set of recommended and/or mandatory SOPs required to establish a functional TRE federation, alongside templates or a lightweight framework that would accelerate drafting and finalisation within TRE federations.
Legal framework	<p>EOSC-ENTRUST model agreements (“peer-to-peer” and “consortium agreement”) are missing.</p> <p>The impact that the EHDS implementation will have on current roles and responsibilities should be discussed in more detail.</p>
Roles	<p>Change “Data Controller” from a fixed actor to a role that can be assumed by different entities depending on dataset, jurisdiction, and legal agreements.</p> <p>Introduce a Data Access Committee role/capability responsible for reviewing and approving data access requests.</p> <p>Driver 3 suggests creating a separate Software Approver role within TRE governance to handle software validation and approval processes.</p> <p>Output control responsibilities must be defined at the federation level, particularly for federated analyses spanning multiple TREs. Potentially consider adding a “Lead TRE” role that would coordinate output control across federated analysis projects.</p> <p>Create training and user support roles both at TRE governance and federation governance level.</p>
Terminology	<p>Maintain distinct lists for abbreviations (acronyms and short forms) and for terminology (concepts and their definitions).</p> <p>Whenever possible, reuse authoritative</p>

	<p>definitions (e.g., legal texts, community efforts) from established sources rather than creating new ones.</p> <p>When a suitable definition already exists, use it as-is unless there is a strong need to adapt it.</p> <p>Deliver a harmonised EOSC-ENTRUST glossary.</p>
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6.4 Driver 4: Public-Private interactions between TRE in health and environmental data

6.4.1 Prototype description

The Driver 4 prototype aims to design a proof-of-concept for federating two TREs to enable developing machine learning models or used separately to create synthetic data.

The prototype development includes two steps:

- For the first phase we have imported sensitive data to the SD Services of CSC (SD Desktop and SD Connect). The data originates from a local sports institute and it contains personal and training information of football and floorball players. The players have given consent for research use. We have installed synthetic data creation software in the SPE and created synthetic data. We have exported data and synthetic data creation machine learning models from the SD Desktop.

The tasks in this are the following:

- 1) The synthetic data creation software is reliable so that it can be allowed in the SPE
 - 2) The data and models that are exported do not contain sensitive information
- Second, a proof-of-concept is designed to represent requirements, workflows and governance practices for creating machine learning models with federated learning (FL) across federated TREs. To define a detailed enough description two specific environments are chosen: CSC's SD Services and the Turku University of Applied Science's environment. For this we plan to use anonymous medical image data.

Federated learning is an emerging technology that can be used to train a global model by building local models and then combining them. During training the global model can be created many times and it will then be distributed to local nodes for further training. The data does not move from the local environments.

The challenges in this are the following:

- 1) Identification of the partners so that they can be trusted
- 2) Organizing safe communication between participating TREs during training
- 3) Protecting the learning parameters, like neural network weights during transfer (e.g. with homomorphic encryption)
- 4) Ensuring the reliability of the training algorithms so that no sensitive data is leaked (e.g. with differential privacy)

6.4.2 Gap analysis

Architecture specifications

- In Driver 4 we identified that Authentication, Authorisation, Accounting, and Identification aspects need refinement. WP17–19 are working on this (AAAI), and they are building the blueprint on existing AAAI, thus, we expect the refinement to come from that work.
- We also note a need for refinement in the capability of multi-party computation: federal analytics and federated learning. There is a need to make the division of computation into several TREs feasible. This is being addressed in the architectural design.
- We also note a gap for implementation in terms of workflows for job submission within the federation. There is a need for a unified job submission service already mentioned in the Architecture Blueprint, however, the description is still on a high level in the architecture and perhaps a more detailed description needs to be addressed in the Technologies WP.

SOPs

- In Driver 4, we identified a gap with the process for the division of costs. The computation environment will have costs, and it needs to be defined how to account for these. The parties must address this,
- There is also a need to consider further what it means to share data across borders. There is a desire to be a federation across Europe as a whole, but it's not that easy.
- We have to align this project with other European projects

Legal framework

- In Driver 4 we have encountered IP issues. Private companies may own the original data which is the base for synthetic data created in TREs. The companies want to benefit from their data and they want to contractually control the use of synthetic data. The IP issues related to commercial interests need to be considered in further work. The companies' legal demands would have to be aligned with the consortium agreement and terminology.
- Companies may want to use the TREs because they do not have the resources or skills to perform analyses themselves. They may be interested to hire a TRE operator to do the studies and processing without becoming a member of the consortium. This kind of relationship should be included.
- Local laws may contradict with TRE specifications. They should be aligned with the EHDS initiative.
- There is also a lack of clarity on the relations between the companies and the federation. If a company's data is being processed, would the company become a contractual party to the federation? Does the federation acknowledge an entity with

an indirect link to the federation? Does this role need to be recognised in the Blueprint?

Roles

- In Driver 4 we have analyzed the roles from the Blueprint with regard to our setup:
 - Data User = Data Controller, depending on the agreement with the company.
 - Data Manager at CSC.
 - SPE owner = TRE Provider & TRE Operator, also at CSC: TRE architect, developer and support staff, compliance officer
 - Data originator, the players from whom data is collected by the company.
 - Federation operator, could be national or organizational.
- We found that in some cases it was difficult to define the roles and whether the role was taken up by the TRE staff or the company. In Driver 4, the company roles would be defined by agreements to justify billing from services between partners, so the roles should be clarified.
- We are unsure whether SPE owner might be a legal role for checking that the consortium agreement is followed
- For federated learning the TRE roles may require adjusting, but the technology is not ready and tested yet so this cannot be exactly known now

Terminology

- Driver 4 successfully aligned our roles with the Blueprint roles. The Data controller role is defined in the contract with the company who provides the data – however, we were not sure that the Blueprint recognizes shared data controllership.
- The relationship between actors and roles, and also the difference between participants and actors could be clarified. All the roles should be defined in the project, not just the GDPR roles.
- The architecture images are not fully understandable, unless one knows the different icon and colour definitions. The glossary should include some guidance on how to read the architecture images.

6.4.3 Summary of gaps

Topic	Gap(s)
Architecture specifications	Communication Details about different computation models Authentication, Authorisation, Accounting and

	Identification methods
SOPs	Division of costs Sharing data across borders
Legal framework	IP issues must be handled by agreements Companies might want to be clients to TRE operators, not consortium members. How to define this relationship in the consortium agreement
Roles	The roles should be defined more precisely regarding the company-TRE relationship SPE owner role should be defined clearer: is it a legal role for checking that the CA is followed Undefined for FL
Terminology	The relationship between actors and roles, and also the difference between participants and actors could be clarified

7. Results & Discussion

7.1 Summary of the prototypes

The four Drivers collectively illustrate how federated Trusted Research Environments (TREs) can support secure, cross-border research across highly sensitive data domains, while respecting data locality, governance constraints, and disciplinary needs.

Driver 1 provides a technically focused proof-of-concept, demonstrating that complex genomic analyses can be executed in a federated manner by running a shared, containerised variant-calling workflow across multiple TREs. By relying on workflow standardisation (nf-core/SAREK), GA4GH TES-based interoperability, and emerging provenance standards such as RO-Crate, this Driver establishes early technical feasibility and exposes genomics-specific governance and scalability challenges that must be addressed for end-to-end federation.

Driver 2 shifts the emphasis from distributed execution to federated access, showing how trusted third-party secure infrastructures can act as practical federation hubs for sensitive social science data. Through pilots with GESIS, the UK Data Service, and TARKI using the SANE platform, it demonstrates that centrally operated, highly secure environments can significantly lower legal, technical, and organisational barriers to cross-national research, particularly benefiting institutions that lack the capacity to operate full TREs.

Driver 3 applies federation to real-world health research by linking RCT and large-scale real-world data across national TREs in Norway and Scotland. By synthesising individual participant data from the EU-COVAT-1 trial with population-level vaccination records, this Driver not only tests analytical approaches for cross-TRE studies but also addresses the scientific question of how well RCT findings generalise to real populations, feeding directly into requirements for the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint.

Driver 4 looks ahead to emerging analytical paradigms, developing proof-of-concepts for privacy-preserving machine learning and synthetic data generation across federated TREs. Through secure experimentation within CSC's SD Services and planned federated learning between CSC and Turku University of Applied Sciences, it highlights how advanced techniques such as federated learning, homomorphic encryption, and differential privacy can enable innovation without exposing sensitive data. Taken together, the Drivers form a coherent progression from technical feasibility, to access models, to applied health research, and finally to advanced analytics providing rich, cross-disciplinary evidence on how federated TREs can be operationalised within a future EOSC-aligned ecosystem.

7.2 Results gap analysis

7.2.1 Architecture specifications & SOPs

Architecture specifications

Validation of the second year Architecture specifications showed that most architecture components needed for a federated network of TREs are now included in the Blueprint. The discussion revealed some remaining gaps that mainly center around how the components work together to support federated analysis in an end-to-end lifecycle, through policies, operational rules and compliance requirements. In addition, suggestions for refinement of existing Blueprint components were made.

For clarity, architecture components that are missing in the second year Blueprint, or that need further refinement, are discussed here. Specific policies are discussed in the SOPs section.

Aspect	Key results / agreements	Identified gaps
Federation rule book containing policies	A <i>Federation Rulebook</i> , capturing common policies, operational rules, and compliance requirements for all federation participants, needs to be provided.	<i>Federation Rulebook</i> should contain policies for: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• SDC• Federation trust and interoperability mechanics• Certification Process of TREs joining the federation
Cost management	The Blueprint does not specify how to account for computation environment costs, particularly when sharing results and data across borders.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Cost management component at federation and TRE levels
Federated analysis	Components that support federated analysis need further refinement. This includes how computations are distributed and how intermediate results are stored.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• End-to-end data lifecycle patterns for federated analysis• Intermediary storage definition, needed for multi-step workflow execution

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distinguish between job submission interfaces within the federation vs to outside clients
AAAI	Separate Index Services from Linking Services to comply with different legal frameworks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Separately defined Linking Service • Best practices / methods for AAAI
Software Service	The Software Service would benefit from detailing how users and TREs interact with the service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use and/or availability of software licences • Version management • Authorisation of tool/workflow requests per TRE • Centralized software provisioning

SOPs

The discussion on SOPs did reveal some SOPs that TREs and/or a TRE federation would need, but that have not yet been included in the Blueprint. However, the most important result was that TREs will need SOPs that are detailed and specific to their own regulatory framework. To ensure interoperability, the ENTRUST Federation would need a *framework* for developing SOPs, rather than SOPs for individual TREs to follow. This framework could include best practices, policies and a list of SOPs that TREs minimally need to be able to join the federation.

In the table below, the *SOP Framework* is listed together with aspects of SOPs or policies that TREs within the federation would need to agree on.

Aspect	Key results / agreements	Identified gaps
SOP Framework	Individual Drivers / TREs will need very specific and detailed SOPs for their daily operations. These cannot be standardized, but a framework for developing SOPs is needed in the federation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Framework for development of SOPs • List of minimally required SOPs needed to join the federation • Best practices / policies

Data Life Cycle	SOPs should cover the full data lifecycle aligned to user stories: ingestion, processing, access, analysis, output generation, archiving, data release, withdrawal, and off-boarding.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• No federation-wide data lifecycle framework.• No agreed minimum archiving standards (duration, scope, responsibility).• Lack of federation guidance on data withdrawal, including cascading impacts across TREs.
Tooling	Tooling, workflows, and software approval are TRE-specific and domain-dependent. The federation defines shared principles and processes for tooling approval, veto, and risk assessment, rather than maintaining centrally approved tool lists, allowing local autonomy while ensuring consistency.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Workflow/tool approval process for cross-TRE execution.• Limited clarity on responsibilities when workflows span multiple TREs or QMZs.
SDC processes	TREs apply different SDC rules due to varying data sensitivity and legal contexts. Output checking remains the responsibility of the TRE releasing outputs. Special attention needed for outputs derived from multiple datasets across multiple TREs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• No agreed federation-level SDC process framework.• No solution for coordinating output checking across TREs in complex federated analyses.• No shared guidance on risks such as inference, or re-identification attacks.• Limited federation guidance on reproducibility-oriented models (e.g. Blind SANE).

AAAI	Federation should support a consistent researcher journey for discovery and access requests. User certification is a core trust mechanism and should be performed at TRE level, based on agreed federation criteria.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Best practice SOPs for AAAI • User training & certification linked to AAAI
Workflow processing	Workflow execution capabilities differ across TREs; federation should not mandate uniform implementation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federation SOPs for workflow orchestration across TREs. • Unclear placement of job submission services (TRE-internal vs federation-level). • No agreed cost-sharing or accounting model for compute and storage usage.

7.2.2 Legal framework

The legal breakout session showed that while GDPR provides a common foundation, current practices remain fragmented and nationally driven, limiting the scalability of cross-border TRE federations. Consortium agreements are widely seen as the most suitable model, but their implementation is constrained by divergent national interpretations, unclear role and liability allocation, and gaps in output control, breach handling, and commercial participation. The table below summarises the key legal aspects, highlighting agreed approaches and remaining gaps that need to be addressed to enable sustainable federation models.

Aspect	Key results / agreements	Identified gaps
Agreement models: peer-to-peer vs consortium agreement	Consortium agreement is seen as advantageous for a federation, but apart from existing networks (EGA), peer-to-peer agreements are current common practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer-to-peer agreements do not scale and create significant legal and administrative burden in cross-border federations. • Lack of harmonised, reusable consortium agreement templates

		<p>suitable for trans-national TRE federations beyond existing networks.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Legal clarity is missing on how consortium agreements should interact with DPAs, DAAs, and national frameworks.
Output control and responsibility for research outputs	Most existing agreements focus on data access rather than downstream outputs. Output checking and controlled release mechanisms are increasingly recognised as essential components of TRE governance, particularly in “data-stays-at-source” and federated models.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• No harmonised legal or operational model for output checking across federations.• Responsibilities and liabilities for outputs (e.g., publications, derived datasets) are often unclear or omitted from agreements.
Breach notification and liability in federated settings	Data breach protocols exist in some initiatives (e.g. FEAGA), usually as supporting documents rather than part of core agreements. GDPR provides a general framework for breach notification and accountability.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Lack of shared responsibility models and standardised clauses covering incident response, notification timelines, and cross-border accountability.
National legal frameworks and cross-border harmonisation	GDPR provides the overarching legal basis for processing sensitive data, complemented by national legislation and sector-specific rules. EHDS is expected to introduce more harmonised governance for secondary use of health data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Divergent national legal interpretations and additional requirements create misalignment, hindering harmonised agreement templates and slowing cross-border federation implementation• Blueprint lacks clear guidance on how to operationalise compliance

		across heterogeneous legal regimes.
Commercial participation and IP rights	Commercial partners may contribute data, generate synthetic data, or access TRE services via federation members. IP ownership, subcontracting chains, and indirect participation models are recognised as legitimate use cases.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current agreement models insufficiently address commercial roles, IP ownership of derived or synthetic data, and company participation without federation membership. • Blueprint lacks clarity on how such actors are contractually recognised and governed.
Consent, legal basis, and EHDS transition	Consent remains the legal basis for many clinical research datasets, while public interest or official authority is used for routinely collected healthcare data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blueprint underestimates the impact of changing legal bases under EHDS on roles, SOPs, and agreement structures.

7.2.3 Roles and common terminology

The Roles & Terminology breakout session on Day 2 focused on validating the role model and terminology used in the EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint against current Driver practices. Discussions highlighted the need for a clear and consistent distinction between actors (participating entities) and roles (functions and responsibilities), as well as the importance of accommodating national and organisational differences in how responsibilities are assigned. While there was broad agreement on the overall direction of the Blueprint, the session identified several inconsistencies, ambiguities, and missing elements related to role definitions, terminology usage, and visual representations. The outcomes of this breakout informed a consolidated gap analysis, summarised in the table below.

Roles

Aspect	Key results / agreements	Identified gaps
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Roles vs Actors distinction	Clear distinction between Actors (entities participating in the federation) and Roles (functions and responsibilities) was validated as essential for clarity and flexibility.	The distinction is not yet applied consistently across Blueprint text, tables, diagrams, and glossary, leading to ambiguity.
Role implementation across contexts	Acknowledgement that the same functional role (e.g. output control, software approval) may be assigned to different actors depending on national, organisational, or TRE context.	The Blueprint does not sufficiently reflect multiple valid implementations or provide guidance on equivalence between roles across contexts.
GDPR-defined roles	Consensus that GDPR-defined legal roles (e.g. Data Controller, Data Processor, Joint Controller) should be used as-is and not redefined in the Blueprint.	Non-GDPR operational roles are sometimes mixed with legal roles, creating potential confusion or legal ambiguity.
User-related roles	Agreement that user-related roles must be more clearly differentiated to support access control and responsibility assignment.	Ambiguity remains around user categories, privileges, and responsibilities within workflows.
Training & support roles	Training and user support recognised as essential operational roles within federated TREs.	Responsibilities between TRE-level and federation-level training and support are not yet clearly defined.
Commercial & industry roles	Recognition that companies and commercial actors may participate in federation scenarios.	Company-specific roles (e.g. IP owner, commercial partner) are not clearly represented in the Blueprint role model.
Blueprint diagrams & icons	Visual role representations are useful for shared understanding.	Several role icons and symbols in Blueprint diagrams lack explicit definitions or links to textual descriptions.

Common Terminology

Aspect	Key results / agreements	Identified gaps
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Terminology alignment	Agreement to use shared umbrella terms in the Blueprint, with local, national, or domain-specific terms mapped to them.	Terminology is applied inconsistently across Blueprint sections, tables, diagrams, and glossary entries.
Use of non-GDPR terms	Recognition that some operational terms do not exist in GDPR and require careful treatment in the Blueprint.	Terms such as “data custodian” are used without clear definition or alignment with legal terminology.
Synonyms & equivalents	Agreement that equivalent terms for the same role or concept (e.g. output checker) should be listed to reflect different implementations.	The Blueprint lacks a systematic list of synonyms and equivalent terms across Drivers and countries.
Definition of key concepts	Recognition that clear definitions of core concepts (e.g. “project”, “user”) are critical for correct interpretation.	Key concepts are not consistently or sufficiently defined across the Blueprint and glossary.
External alignment	Agreement to align terminology with external standards and initiatives (e.g. GDPR, EHDS, domain-specific glossaries).	Alignment with external terminologies is still partial and requires systematic review.
Glossary governance	Consensus on collaboratively refining the glossary using shared tooling and a defined process.	Governance, versioning, and ownership of the glossary are not yet fully defined.

7.4 Updated generic User Journey

In the second Blueprint report, the Architecture WP analyzed the generic user journey and made the following recommendations for updates (shortened):

- **Iterative Research:** The user journey must support a non-linear analysis process, allowing researchers to refine analyses, request new software, or add data sources after starting a Project.
- **Federation Scope:** The journey must include analysis across multiple TREs, not just a single TRE. Federation Governance should manage distributed data access requests and coordinate multi-party agreements.

- **Terminology and Focus:** Drivers advised shifting focus from simple “export” to Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC).
- **Missing Steps:** Missing administrative and support steps include cost management and payment, explicit Project start procedures, and admin functions for assigning user roles. Dedicated user support is needed at both TRE and federation levels.

These gaps were addressed as follows (see Figure 1 for the updated generic user journey):

- **Iterative Research:** The user journey is already set up to allow for iterative research. Steps to add additional data and/or software to TREs are included in the overarching “data analysis” phase to allow for iteration. To make this clear, the *data analysis* phase was renamed *data analysis (iterative)*.
- **Federation Scope:** The user journey allows for analysis across multiple TREs by including a *Federation Governance* layer. To address the coordination of agreements more clearly, the federation governance step *Coordinate signing of multiple data use agreements* was renamed *Coordinate multi-party agreements*. In the *Data preparation and provisioning* phase, a *Coordinate multi-TRE access* step was added to account for AAAI in a federated context. In addition, the following steps in the federation governance layer are relevant for federated analysis:
 - Data discovery phase: receive and distribute federated query
 - Data access application phase: Distribute data access requests to TREs
 - Data analysis (iterative) phase: Distribute analysis to multiple TREs
 - Results Output phase: Gather individual TRE results, Send results to project space and Aggregate individual TRE results (data user step)
- **Terminology and Focus:** The *Perform SDC* step reflects the Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) terminology.
- **Missing Steps:** Cost management and payment steps were added to the updated user journey, as well as *Initiate Project* and *End Project* steps. In addition, the step *Give data user access to project space* was renamed *Assign user roles*. Dedicated user support was added throughout the user journey at both TRE and federation levels.

Figure 1: Updated user journey incorporating recommendations from the second EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint report. Newly added steps show a thick black border. Yellow and blue bars below the figure reflect ongoing user support throughout the user journey on both the TRE governance and Federation Governance levels.

8. Conclusions

8.1 Main results

Architecture specifications

The architecture specifications highlight the need for stronger federation-wide alignment and clearer technical definitions. A comprehensive Federation Rulebook is required to consolidate common policies on SDCs, trust and interoperability mechanisms, TRE certification, and cost management, as these are currently incomplete or implicit. The

Blueprint lacks clarity on how computation and infrastructure costs are managed, particularly for cross-border federated analyses, indicating the need for cost management components at both federation and TRE levels. Key architectural gaps remain in support for federated analysis, including end-to-end data lifecycle patterns, intermediary storage for multi-step workflows, and clear separation between internal federation job submission interfaces and those for external clients. In addition, AAI components require refinement, notably the separation of Index and Linking Services to meet legal requirements and the establishment of best practices. Finally, the Software Service layer needs clearer specifications around licensing, version management, authorisation of tools and workflows per TRE, and more centralized software provisioning to ensure consistency and reproducibility across the federation.

SOPs

The discussions confirmed that SOPs must remain TRE-specific and aligned with national regulatory frameworks, and therefore cannot be standardised at federation level. The framework should focus on developing SOPs, including best practices, policy guidance, and a minimal set of SOP areas required for participation in the federation. Federation-level alignment should focus on shared principles and processes, rather than identical rules, to support interoperability across areas such as the data lifecycle, tooling approval, SDC, AAI, and workflow processing. Several gaps remain, notably the lack of federation guidance on data lifecycle management, tooling and workflow approval, cross-TRE SDC, user certification, and cost-sharing, which should be addressed through a federation SOP framework and rulebook.

Legal Framework

The legal breakout confirmed that GDPR provides a necessary common foundation, but current legal practices remain fragmented, nationally driven, and largely project-based, limiting the scalability of cross-border TRE federations. There was broad agreement that consortium agreements offer the most suitable legal basis for federated models, yet their adoption is constrained by divergent national interpretations, lack of harmonised templates, and unclear interaction with DPAs, DAAs, and emerging EHDS requirements. Key gaps were identified in output control, breach notification, commercial participation, and consent management, indicating the need for clearer, more operational legal guidance to support sustainable and interoperable federation models.

Roles & Terminology

The Roles & Terminology breakout showed strong alignment on the overall role model proposed in the Blueprint, particularly the need to clearly distinguish between actors and roles and to use GDPR-defined legal roles without reinterpretation. Participants agreed that flexibility is required to accommodate different national and organisational

implementations, and that shared umbrella terms can support this diversity. However, significant gaps remain due to inconsistent application of roles and terminology across Blueprint text, diagrams, and the glossary, unclear treatment of user-related and commercial roles, and the absence of a governed, systematically maintained terminology framework. Addressing these gaps is essential to improve clarity, interoperability, and correct legal interpretation across federated TRE environments.

8.2 Recommendations for the final EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint

Architecture Specifications

- **Develop a federation rulebook:** A federation rulebook should both contain the conditions for joining the federation and policies about how the federation operates.
- **Distinguish between index services and linking services** to support the distinction between these services in terms of responsibilities in some legal frameworks.
- **Refine and clarify the software service and federated workflow execution** to give TREs more detail on how they can interact with these services.

SOPs

- TREs will need their own detailed SOPs to describe their internal processes. However, to support interoperability it is recommended to include **a framework for developing and maintaining SOPs** in the Blueprint, as well as an inventory of which SOPs are minimally required for the federation to function. Therefore, the Drivers recommend the following:
- **Develop a federation-level SOP framework**, defining shared principles, minimum required SOP areas, and best practices to support interoperability, while leaving detailed operational SOPs to individual TREs.
- **Focus on process equivalence and transparency rather than standardisation**, requiring TREs to document local practices and capabilities so cross-TRE research can operate predictably within the federation.

Legal framework

- **Implement a layered agreement approach:** Combine a harmonised, federation-level consortium agreement with peer-to-peer agreements where needed, allowing incremental onboarding while ensuring consistency, scalability, and cross-border interoperability.
- **Standardise roles and accountability across models:** Define clear, GDPR-aligned roles, responsibilities, and liability rules (including output control and breach handling) that apply consistently to both consortium and peer-to-peer agreements, while allowing limited national adaptations.

Roles and common terminology

The discussion on roles and common terminology revealed that both Drivers and individual TREs will continue to use terms that accurately reflect their unique situation. To foster interoperability in a federation of TREs, it is therefore paramount to map terms that are in use at individual TREs and in specific research areas or Drivers to terminology used within the federation. In addition, the ENTRUST glossary should be jointly agreed-upon within the project and aligned with relevant external frameworks where possible.

- **Standardise role definitions while allowing contextual implementation:** Apply a clear and consistent distinction between actors and roles across the Blueprint, using GDPR-defined roles as-is and providing guidance on equivalent role implementations across different national and organisational contexts.
- **Establish a governed, harmonised glossary:** Adopt shared umbrella terms aligned with GDPR, EHDS, and relevant domain standards, supported by a maintained glossary that maps synonyms, national variants, and equivalent terms. Define core concepts consistently and introduce clear governance, versioning, and ownership processes to ensure coherent and sustained terminology alignment across the Blueprint.

9. Next steps

Upon delivery of this report, the third and last project year of EOSC-ENTRUST starts. In the third year the focus of the project lies on demonstrating the impact of the ENTRUST Blueprint and building the TRE network. For the Drivers, specifically, showing how the Drivers have adopted the Blueprint is central and shown through (1) a final set of Driver requirements (M9) and (2) a dissemination package of real-world exemplars (D9.1) that can help use cases from outside the project to implement the ENTRUST Blueprint.

Adoption of the Blueprint by the Drivers is heavily reliant on the level of adoption among the TREs that the Drivers work with. The *Requirements Management Framework*, developed in the Providers Forum (WP11) parallel to this deliverable, will play an important role in aligning Drivers and Providers and in quantifying adoption. It does this in two ways:

1. The Requirements Management Framework provides a framework through which fulfillment of the Drivers' requirements can be measured, thus aligning Drivers' requirements and TREs' capabilities
2. Through making the Drivers' requirements actionable, adoption becomes quantifiable

Not all Drivers' requirements are directly linked to federation readiness. Therefore, a maturity model to measure federation-readiness of TREs might be beneficial in addition to the Requirements Management Framework.

This report included the latest updated version of the generic user journey, including refinements proposed by the Architecture WP. To gain more clarity on how well this user journey fits a myriad of use cases and to support implementation, the Drivers aim to make the user journey publicly available. This will allow researchers and TREs to analyse it in relation to their processes and provide feedback from outside the project itself.

Finally, this report highlighted multiple gaps in terminology. The EOSC-ENTRUST glossary is still under development by the Architecture WP. During the third project year, the Drivers will contribute to completing the glossary in collaboration with other WPs. This is detailed work that will take place in the project-internal glossary document.